

Real-Time High-Fidelity Algorithms for Bayesian Inverse Problems Involving Shift-Invariant Systems

Sreeram Venkat^{a,*}, Stefan Henneking^a, Milinda Fernando^a, Omar Ghattas^a

^a*Oden Institute, University of Texas at Austin, 201 E 24th St, Austin, TX 78712, USA*

Abstract

As a means of providing early warning for tsunamis, we aim to create digital twins for the Cascadia subduction zone (CSZ) with the following properties: (1) they employ discretizations of high-fidelity models governed by partial differential equations (PDEs), leading to extreme scale forward problems; (2) they solve an inverse problem to assimilate observational data to infer uncertain model components followed by a forward prediction of the evolving dynamics; (3) the entire end-to-end data-to-inference-to-prediction computation is carried out in real time through a Bayesian framework that rigorously accounts for uncertainties. The creation of such digital twins is faced with several challenges that stem from extreme physical scale and slow eigenvalue decay of the governing equations. In this paper, we introduce a methodology to overcome these challenges by exploiting the autonomous structure of the forward model to amortize the majority of the cost of solving the Bayesian inverse problem. Specifically, we present the implementation and performance results of a multi-GPU-accelerated FFT-based algorithm that computes lightning-fast Hessian matrix-vector products (Hessian matvecs), paving the way toward real-time Bayesian inference.

Keywords: Large-scale Bayesian inference, Autonomous systems, Block Toeplitz, HPC

1. Motivation and Background

Tsunamis resulting from megathrust earthquakes have taken the lives of millions and caused hundreds of billions of dollars in damages. Acoustic pressure sensors mounted on the seafloor can provide real-time data for early warning systems that can help prevent the loss of life and thereby reduce the impact of future tsunami events. The key to designing such a system lies in the ability to infer the spatiotemporal seafloor deformation in real time from the pressure data. This inferred deformation can then be used to predict the trajectory of a potential tsunami.

To this end, we aim to create a digital twin for the CSZ. However, we are met with several challenges. A reasonable discretization of the CSZ gives rise to a system with $\mathcal{O}(10^{10})$ parameters and a formal flop count of $\mathcal{O}(10^{30})!$ Developing accurate and predictive surrogates over a 10^{10} -dimensional parameter space for tsunami dynamics described by hyperbolic PDEs is seemingly intractable; such systems do not admit low-dimensional subspace representations. However, we can circumvent these challenges by exploiting the intrinsic structure of the problem and amortizing most of the computationally expensive parts of the Bayesian inverse problem. As a key component of this framework, we outline a multi-GPU-accelerated FFT-based algorithm for computing Hessian matvecs that provides a $\sim 5,000\times$ speedup over conventional methods (after a one-time setup cost).

*Student Contributor

Email addresses: srvenkat@utexas.edu (Sreeram Venkat), stefan@oden.utexas.edu (Stefan Henneking), milinda@oden.utexas.edu (Milinda Fernando), omar@oden.utexas.edu (Omar Ghattas)

Forward Problem: Acoustic-Gravity Wave Equations. The tsunami dynamics are modeled by PDEs (1) that couple ocean acoustic and surface gravity wave propagation [1]:

$$\begin{cases} \rho \partial_t \mathbf{u} + \nabla p = \mathbf{0}, & K^{-1} \partial_t p + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, & \Omega \times (0, T) \\ p = \rho g \eta, & \partial_t \eta = \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}, & \Gamma_s \times (0, T) \end{cases} \left| \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\partial_t b, & \Gamma_b \times (0, T) \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = Z^{-1} p, & \Gamma_a \times (0, T) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

with homogeneous initial conditions, where \mathbf{u} is velocity, p is pressure, η is surface wave height, K and ρ are respectively the bulk modulus and density of seawater, $Z = \rho c$ is the acoustic wave impedance, $c = \sqrt{K/\rho}$ is the speed of sound in seawater, and b is ocean bathymetry; the spatial domain is denoted by Ω with boundaries Γ_s (sea surface), Γ_b (sea bottom), and Γ_a (lateral, absorbing boundaries); $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the outward unit normal; and the temporal domain is $(0, T)$.

Bayesian Inverse Problem (BIP): Define the parameter field as $m := \partial_t b(\mathbf{x}, t)$, data $d = d(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and the parameter-to-observable (p2o) map $\mathcal{F} : m \mapsto d$ mapping parameters to data by solving the forward PDE model (1) with the given parameters and extracting pressure time series at discrete sensor locations. \mathcal{F}^* denotes the corresponding adjoint p2o map, which maps data to parameters by solving the adjoint PDEs to (1).

The goal of solving the BIP is to determine the posterior measure μ_{post} of the parameters given data. Bayes' Rule states that $d\mu_{\text{post}}/d\mu_{\text{prior}} \propto \pi_{\text{like}}(d|m) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|\mathcal{F}m - d\|_{\Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1}}^2\right)$. Assuming a Gaussian prior $m \sim \mathcal{N}(m_{\text{prior}}, \Gamma_{\text{prior}})$, linear p2o map \mathcal{F} , and observations $d = \mathcal{F}m + \nu$, $\nu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Gamma_{\text{noise}})$, the posterior can be analytically expressed as $\mu_{\text{post}} = \mathcal{N}(m_{\text{map}}, \Gamma_{\text{post}})$. Thus, determining the posterior measure amounts to calculating m_{map} and Γ_{post} via (2) [2]. For brevity, we show only the discrete form of the equations; the infinite-dimensional expressions take the same form with the appropriate operators/functions in place of the discrete matrices/vectors.

$$\Gamma_{\text{post}} = \left(\mathbf{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} \mathbf{F} + \Gamma_{\text{prior}}^{-1}\right)^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{m}_{\text{map}} = \Gamma_{\text{post}} \left(\mathbf{F}^* \Gamma_{\text{noise}}^{-1} \mathbf{d} + \Gamma_{\text{prior}}^{-1} \mathbf{m}_{\text{prior}}\right). \quad (2)$$

2. Methods

For problems where the rank of $\mathbf{H} := \Gamma_{\text{post}}^{-1}$ is high (e.g. hyperbolic systems like the acoustic-gravity wave equations), it takes many iterations for an iterative solver such as Conjugate Gradient to converge on (2). Moreover, each application of \mathbf{H} requires a forward and adjoint PDE solve, which is expensive and precludes real-time inference. However, there is an alternative: the tsunami dynamics are governed by an *autonomous system* whose evolution does not have explicit time-dependence. This fact (and causality) manifests in the time-shift invariance of the p2o map \mathcal{F} , which results in the discrete \mathbf{F} being a *block lower-triangular Toeplitz* matrix, enabling extremely fast and efficient matvecs with \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* (see below). In the following 3-phase plan for real-time inference, N_t refers to the number of time steps in the discrete parameter field, data, and PDE state variables; N_m refers to the number of spatial degrees of freedom in the discrete parameter field and N_d to the number of sensor locations. For the CSZ digital twin, $N_t \sim 10^4$, $N_m \sim 10^6$, and $N_d \sim 10^2$.

Phase 1 (offline): Compute the p2o map from adjoint PDE solutions. The time-shift invariance of the PDEs (1) means that only one adjoint PDE solve per sensor location is required to create \mathbf{F} . These adjoint PDEs are solved backward in time with pressure ‘‘sources’’ at each sensor location. Translating these solutions in time gives the entire \mathbf{F} . The block Toeplitz structure of \mathbf{F} also reduces the memory requirements to store it by a factor of N_t . This means only ~ 80 GB memory is required to store \mathbf{F} instead of ~ 800 TB!

Phase 2 (offline): Compute a compact representation of Γ_{post} . For the full-scale model, the discretized parameter dimension is $N_m N_t \sim 10^{10}$. The forward model (1) is hyperbolic, prohibiting the effectiveness of traditional low-rank decomposition methods. To circumvent this issue, we

employ the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula, with which $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}$ from (2) can be rewritten as $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{prior}}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{F}^*\mathbf{K}^{-1}\mathbf{F}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{prior}})$, where $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{noise}} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{prior}}\mathbf{F}^*$. Expressing $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}$ in this form shifts the problem of inverting an operator of size $N_m N_t$ to one of size $N_d N_t$. For the CSZ digital twin, this corresponds to a matrix \mathbf{K} of size $10^6 \times 10^6$, whereas the original $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}$ was of size $10^{10} \times 10^{10}$. The rank of $\mathbf{F}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{prior}}\mathbf{F}^*$ is also at most $\mathcal{O}(N_d N_t) \sim 10^6$, and will likely be lower (we cannot expect every spatiotemporal data point to be informative). So, we can precompute compact representations of this operator to use in the real-time inversion.

Phase 3 (online): Real-time computation of the MAP point. We can now calculate the MAP point \mathbf{m}_{map} in real time using $\mathbf{m}_{\text{map}} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{noise}}^{-1}\mathbf{F}^*\mathbf{d}$ (the noise covariance is assumed to be diagonal). To quantify uncertainty, we use stochastic methods to precompute the diagonal of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}$ (pointwise variance) [3]. The surface wave height forecast $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ is then computed by pushing the inverted parameter field through a prediction map $\mathbf{F}_{\text{pred}} : \mathbf{m} \mapsto \boldsymbol{\eta}$, yielding its distribution, $\mu_{\text{post}(\boldsymbol{\eta})} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{pred}}\mathbf{m}_{\text{map}}, \mathbf{F}_{\text{pred}}\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\text{post}}\mathbf{F}_{\text{pred}}^*)$. Moreover, \mathbf{F}_{pred} has the same block lower-triangular Toeplitz structure as \mathbf{F} .

Fast applications of \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* . All of the computations in Phases 2 and 3 involve many matvecs with the discretized \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}^* operators. To enable fast matvecs with these operators, we employ an FFT-based algorithm that has an efficient multi-GPU implementation. The remainder of the paper will discuss this algorithm and its performance results.

By rearranging the order of space and time indices in the discretization, the operator \mathbf{F} can be seen as a matrix with lower-triangular Toeplitz blocks. Each block is diagonalized (once appropriately padded) by the Fourier transform. In the original ordering of space and time indices, the Fourier-transformed matrix is block-diagonal. Applying the same operation to vectors reduces the problem to that of multiplying a block-diagonal matrix with a vector. Efficient algorithms for this exist in cuBLAS (SBGEMV), which we leverage here. Matvecs with \mathbf{F}^* can be done by simply taking the complex conjugate transpose (implicitly) of the matrix entries before computing the block-diagonal matvec. All of these algorithms can be efficiently implemented on a multi-GPU system, enabling lightning-fast matvecs with \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* . The algorithm is detailed in [4]; its steps are summarized below (ReIndex operations are local, with no communication involved):

Broadcast \rightarrow FFT \rightarrow ReIndex 1 \rightarrow SBGEMV \rightarrow ReIndex 2 \rightarrow IFFT \rightarrow Reduction

3. Results

The FFT-based GPU-accelerated p2o map implementation was benchmarked on up to 48 NVIDIA A100 GPUs on TACC’s *Lonestar6* supercomputer for single- and multi-GPU performance (see Figures 1 and 2), with excellent observed performance. For all tests, $N_t = 2,000$.

Figure 1 (left) shows the roofline analysis (obtained from NSight Compute). All major kernels (ReIndex not shown on the roofline plot) achieve 80–85% of the peak memory bandwidth. Note that the apparently poor performance of some kernels (FFT/IFFT(\mathbf{d})) is purely due to the small input size passed to them; these kernels account for less than 1% of the total runtime and do not pose an issue for overall performance. Figure 1 (middle, right) shows single-GPU scaling results for matvecs with \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* . The matvecs scale linearly with increasing parameter and data dimension. Block-diagonal matvecs (SBGEMVs) comprise the majority of the runtime.

Figure 2 (right) shows weak scaling runtimes split over the different steps of the algorithm. The computation costs remain constant as the number of GPUs is increased, and the communication costs increase at a sub-logarithmic rate. Figure 2 (left, middle) depicts the strong and weak scaling efficiencies, which are controlled by the communication costs. For real-time application purposes, what matters is not scalability, but time to solution. The \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* matvecs for 1.92×10^9 parameters and 2×10^4 data on 48 GPUs each take ~ 0.012 seconds (cf. Figure 2). In this metric, our algorithm

vastly outperforms the conventional method of forward/adjoint PDE solves, which take ~ 1 minute for a similarly sized problem of the acoustic-gravity equations ($\sim 5,000\times$ slower).

Figure 1: Single-GPU performance results on an NVIDIA A100 (40 GB) GPU for \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* matvecs.

Figure 2: Multi-GPU strong and weak scaling results on up to 48 NVIDIA A100 GPUs for \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^* matvecs. Strong scaling: $N_m = 210,000$, $N_d = 10$, $N_t = 2,000$. Weak scaling (size per processor): $n_m = 20,000$, $n_d = 10$, $N_t = 2,000$.

4. Conclusion

By exploiting the time invariance inherent to the forward model, we have created a framework for real-time Bayesian inversion at extreme scale while remaining faithful to high-fidelity, physics-based models. As a core component of this framework, we have developed and implemented an algorithm to compute Hessian matvecs at speeds over three orders of magnitude faster than those of conventional methods. In addition to making real-time Hessian matvecs possible, this algorithm can also be used to accelerate offline portions of the computation. Moreover, this framework is applicable to many other classes of problems, including nuclear testing treaty verification, contaminant transport, and atmospheric CO2 monitoring.

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